

INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF ADVANCED RESEARCH IN COMPUTER AND COMMUNICATION ENGINEERING

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Student, Department of Computer Science & Engineering,
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An Intelligent Interview and Assessment Platform**

Volume 14, Issue 10, October 2025

DOI: [10.17148/IJARCCE.2025.141025](https://doi.org/10.17148/IJARCCE.2025.141025)

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